

A GENERAL 3-D ELASTIC CONSTITUTIVE MODEL FOR AN IMPERFECTLY BONDED PERIODIC ANISOTROPIC MULTILAYERED MEDIUM

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ABSTRACT

The flexible interface model can be adopted to model interface bonding conditions between constituent phases of a composite material. By making use of the modified global-local strain relationships, this paper provides a three dimensional constitutive model for an imperfectly bonded periodic multilayered medium, which can be either symmetric or anti-symmetric stratified. Each layer of the medium is assumed to be generally anisotropic with 21 independent elastic moduli and each interface 3 independent bonding parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Analysis on layered media is an important topic in the mechanics of composite materials. Conventionally, a perfect bonding condition between adjacent phases, which suggests the continuity of tractions and displacements across the interfaces, is adopted. However, this assumption is in fact an idealization. Due to anomalies including chemical reactions, voids and flaws, thermal treatments during manufacturing process or damage during service, there might be discontinuities in interfacial displacement fields [1], which seriously affects the overall behavior of the composites.

The actual mechanism of imperfect bonding at interfaces is still unclear. A common way to solve this problem is to introduce an interfacial layer with appropriate properties. So far on imperfect bonding models, characterized by different descriptions of the interfacial layer, include the sliding interface model [2], the flexible interface model [3-7] and the elastic interfacial layer model [8]. It is noted that "sliding interface" instead of "flexible interface" was used by Jun and Jasiuk [6]. However, the nomination made by Aboudi [1] is followed in this paper. Among the aforementioned models, the flexible interface model, which postulates a linear dependence between jumps of displacements and related tractions at interfaces, is reasonable in describing interface bonding conditions.

Up to date, research works on applying flexible interface model to layered media are few. Such works include the comparison of stiffness and compliance of a perfectly lubricated medium by Benvensite [3] and the derivation of stiffness matrix of a partially bonded medium by Aboudi [1]. Both cases were limited to bilaminated media with isotropic phases under the plane strain condition. An improvement was made by Lai and Wang [7] to afford the three dimensional

elastic constitutive relationship for a multilayered medium composed of isotropic layers. This paper is an extension of Lai and Wang's work. For generality, each of the constituent layer is assumed to be generally anisotropic with 21 independent elastic constants. At each interface, three damage parameters are used to represent respectively the averaged normal and tangential degree of adhesion. Thus, the elastic constitutive relationship derived in this paper can model layers possessing homogenized generally anisotropic elastic properties with any degree of adhesion at interfaces.

CLASSIFICATION OF PERIODIC MULTILAYERED MEDIUM

As shown in Fig. 1, the periodic multilayered media can be classified into two types: symmetric or anti-symmetric stratified [7]. Note that a bilaminated layered medium is classified into the symmetric ones. The choice of the representative volume element (RVE) is demonstrated in Fig. 1 as well. The differences between these two types include different selection of the RVE, different definitions of the thickness of the first and the N-th layer in the RVE and different number of independent interfaces (N for anti-symmetric and N-1 for symmetric).

FLEXIBLE INTERFACE MODEL

The flexible interface model, firstly suggested by Jones and Whittier [9], assumes that across the interface, jumps of displacements are linear dependent to related tractions while the continuity of tractions remains. Under the coordinate definition shown in Fig. 2, the interface continuity conditions at the (k-1)-th interface I_{k-1} can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_1^{(k-1)} - u_1^{(k)} &= -R_{I_1}^{(k-1)} \sigma_{13} & u_2^{(k-1)} - u_2^{(k)} &= -R_{I_2}^{(k-1)} \sigma_{23} & u_3^{(k-1)} - u_3^{(k)} &= -R_n^{(k-1)} \sigma_{33} \\
 \sigma_{13}^{(k-1)} &= \sigma_{13}^{(k)} = \sigma_{13} & \sigma_{23}^{(k-1)} &= \sigma_{23}^{(k)} = \sigma_{23} & \sigma_{33}^{(k-1)} &= \sigma_{33}^{(k)} = \sigma_{33}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where σ_{13} , σ_{23} and σ_{33} are constants through the whole RVE. It is known from Eqn (1) that these three terms of stresses are constant within each layer.

Figure 1. Classification of periodic layered media

Figure 2. Coordinate Definition for the RVE

A damage vector at the interface I_k can be constructed by the three proportional constant components at different directions, $R_n^{(k)}$, $R_{I_1}^{(k)}$ and $R_{I_2}^{(k)}$. It is worth mentioning that if the normal traction is compressive ($\sigma_{33} < 0$), the normal displacement will be non-congruence. Imposing

of zero $R_n^{(k)}$ under compression is thus suggested [5]. However, if an initial detachment at the interface is assumed, this parameter can be non-zero under such a condition. Let the total thickness of the RVE be $H = \sum_{k=1}^N \bar{h}_k$, in which \bar{h}_k is the thickness of the k-th layer. The volume fraction of the k-th layer in the RVE is defined as $\varphi_k = \bar{h}_k/H$. In accordance with Green's theorem, the global-local strain and stress relationships are of the forms

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \varphi_k \epsilon_{ij}^{(k)} + \frac{1}{H} \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} R_{i/n}^{(k)} \sigma_{ij}^{(k)} \quad \bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \varphi_k \sigma_{ij}^{(k)} \quad (2)$$

The $\epsilon_{ij}^{(k)}$ and $\sigma_{ij}^{(k)}$ represent respectively the strains and stresses within the k-th layer. The constant Γ serves as an initial value for counting the number of interfaces. That is, $\Gamma=0$ for anti-symmetric media and $\Gamma=1$ for symmetric media, as shown in Fig. 2. Stresses and strains are constant in each homogeneous layer be the RVE subjected to homogeneous distributions of stress and strain. Regarding to the geometry of the layered medium shown in Fig. 2, the displacement field in the k-th layer is a linear function as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_1^{(k)} \\ u_2^{(k)} \\ u_3^{(k)} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13}^{(k)} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{23}^{(k)} \\ A_{31} & A_{32} & A_{33}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \\ X_3 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} B_1^{(k)} \\ B_2^{(k)} \\ B_3^{(k)} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The parameters without upper letter (k) are constant. The $A_{ij}^{(k)}$ are designated the first order coefficients of the displacement field. Recurrent forms for $B_i^{(k)}$ can be further obtained as in Lai and Wang [7]. However, since stresses and strains are the first derivatives of the displacement fields, only the first order coefficients are involved in the elastic constitutive relationship. By assuming each layer being generally anisotropic with 21 independent elastic moduli, the stress distributions within the k-th layer are of the form

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11}^{(k)} \\ \sigma_{22}^{(k)} \\ \sigma_{33}^{(k)} \\ \sigma_{23}^{(k)} \\ \sigma_{13}^{(k)} \\ \sigma_{12}^{(k)} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11}^{(k)} & C_{12}^{(k)} & C_{13}^{(k)} & C_{14}^{(k)} & C_{15}^{(k)} & C_{16}^{(k)} \\ C_{12}^{(k)} & C_{22}^{(k)} & C_{23}^{(k)} & C_{24}^{(k)} & C_{25}^{(k)} & C_{26}^{(k)} \\ C_{13}^{(k)} & C_{23}^{(k)} & C_{33}^{(k)} & C_{34}^{(k)} & C_{35}^{(k)} & C_{36}^{(k)} \\ C_{14}^{(k)} & C_{24}^{(k)} & C_{34}^{(k)} & C_{44}^{(k)} & C_{45}^{(k)} & C_{46}^{(k)} \\ C_{15}^{(k)} & C_{25}^{(k)} & C_{35}^{(k)} & C_{45}^{(k)} & C_{55}^{(k)} & C_{56}^{(k)} \\ C_{16}^{(k)} & C_{26}^{(k)} & C_{36}^{(k)} & C_{46}^{(k)} & C_{56}^{(k)} & C_{66}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} A_{11} \\ A_{22} \\ A_{33}^{(k)} \\ A_{23}^{(k)} + A_{32} \\ A_{13}^{(k)} + A_{31} \\ A_{12}^{(k)} + A_{21} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Rewriting of Eqn (4) with respect to the invariant forms makes

$$\begin{Bmatrix} A_{33}^{(k)} \\ A_{23}^{(k)} + A_{32} \\ A_{13}^{(k)} + A_{31} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{Q_k} \left(\begin{bmatrix} M_{11}^{(k)} & M_{12}^{(k)} & M_{13}^{(k)} \\ M_{12}^{(k)} & M_{22}^{(k)} & M_{23}^{(k)} \\ M_{13}^{(k)} & M_{23}^{(k)} & M_{33}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{13} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} N_{11}^{(k)} & N_{12}^{(k)} & N_{13}^{(k)} \\ N_{21}^{(k)} & N_{22}^{(k)} & N_{23}^{(k)} \\ N_{31}^{(k)} & N_{32}^{(k)} & N_{33}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} A_{11} \\ A_{22} \\ A_{12} + A_{21} \end{Bmatrix} \right) \quad (5)$$

Eqn (5) is important in solving inter-layer stresses and strains. The parameters in Eqn (5) are

$$Q_k = \det \begin{pmatrix} C_{33}^{(k)} & C_{34}^{(k)} & C_{35}^{(k)} \\ C_{34}^{(k)} & C_{44}^{(k)} & C_{45}^{(k)} \\ C_{35}^{(k)} & C_{45}^{(k)} & C_{55}^{(k)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{11}^{(k)} &= C_{44}^{(k)} C_{55}^{(k)} - (C_{45}^{(k)})^2 & M_{22}^{(k)} &= C_{33}^{(k)} C_{55}^{(k)} - (C_{35}^{(k)})^2 & M_{33}^{(k)} &= C_{33}^{(k)} C_{44}^{(k)} - (C_{34}^{(k)})^2 \\
 M_{12}^{(k)} &= C_{35}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{34}^{(k)} C_{55}^{(k)} & M_{13}^{(k)} &= C_{34}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{35}^{(k)} C_{44}^{(k)} & M_{23}^{(k)} &= C_{34}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} - C_{33}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$N_{11}^{(k)} = C_{45}^{(k)} (C_{13}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{14}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} - C_{15}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)}) + C_{55}^{(k)} (C_{14}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)} - C_{13}^{(k)} C_{44}^{(k)}) + C_{15}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} C_{44}^{(k)} \tag{8}$$

$$N_{12}^{(k)} = C_{45}^{(k)} (C_{23}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{24}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} - C_{25}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)}) + C_{55}^{(k)} (C_{24}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)} - C_{23}^{(k)} C_{44}^{(k)}) + C_{25}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} C_{44}^{(k)} \tag{9}$$

$$N_{13}^{(k)} = C_{45}^{(k)} (C_{36}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{46}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} - C_{56}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)}) + C_{55}^{(k)} (C_{46}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)} - C_{36}^{(k)} C_{44}^{(k)}) + C_{56}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} C_{44}^{(k)} \tag{10}$$

$$N_{21}^{(k)} = C_{35}^{(k)} (C_{14}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} - C_{13}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{15}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)}) + C_{33}^{(k)} (C_{15}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{14}^{(k)} C_{55}^{(k)}) + C_{13}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)} C_{55}^{(k)} \tag{11}$$

$$N_{22}^{(k)} = C_{35}^{(k)} (C_{24}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} - C_{23}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{25}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)}) + C_{33}^{(k)} (C_{25}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{24}^{(k)} C_{55}^{(k)}) + C_{23}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)} C_{55}^{(k)} \tag{12}$$

$$N_{23}^{(k)} = C_{35}^{(k)} (C_{46}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} - C_{36}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{56}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)}) + C_{33}^{(k)} (C_{56}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{46}^{(k)} C_{55}^{(k)}) + C_{34}^{(k)} C_{36}^{(k)} C_{55}^{(k)} \tag{13}$$

$$N_{31}^{(k)} = C_{34}^{(k)} (C_{15}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)} - C_{13}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{14}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)}) + C_{44}^{(k)} (C_{13}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} - C_{15}^{(k)} C_{33}^{(k)}) + C_{14}^{(k)} C_{33}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} \tag{14}$$

$$N_{32}^{(k)} = C_{34}^{(k)} (C_{25}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)} - C_{23}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{24}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)}) + C_{44}^{(k)} (C_{23}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} - C_{25}^{(k)} C_{33}^{(k)}) + C_{24}^{(k)} C_{33}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} \tag{15}$$

$$N_{33}^{(k)} = C_{34}^{(k)} (C_{56}^{(k)} C_{34}^{(k)} - C_{36}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} - C_{46}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)}) + C_{44}^{(k)} (C_{36}^{(k)} C_{35}^{(k)} - C_{56}^{(k)} C_{33}^{(k)}) + C_{46}^{(k)} C_{33}^{(k)} C_{45}^{(k)} \tag{16}$$

ELASTIC CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONSHIP

The elastic constitutive relationship can be readily obtained by setting proper homogeneous traction or displacement boundary conditions and by making use of the global-local stress and strain relationships, namely, Eqn (2). Using of such relationships instead of imposing proper boundary conditions as was done by Benveniste [3] and Aboudi [1] greatly simplifies the analysis. For providence, only results of stiffness and compliance matrices are listed here. Detailed derivations and the forms of stress and strain distributions within each layer under specific homogeneous boundary conditions will be appear in a formal paper.

STIFFNESS MATRIX

The stiffness matrix can be gradually evaluated by solving the first order coefficients of the displacement fields under specific homogeneous displacement boundary conditions. Once these coefficients are solved, the global stresses can be readily obtained from the global-local stress relationship, Eqn (2), together with the stress-strain relationship of the constituent layers, Eqn (4). Elements of the stiffness matrix can be evaluated by dividing induced global stresses to the specific global strain. After a lengthy manipulation, the stiffness matrix is obtained as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{11} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{22} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{33} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{23} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{13} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11}^a & C_{12}^a & C_{13}^a & C_{14}^a & C_{15}^a & C_{16}^a \\ C_{12}^a & C_{22}^a & C_{23}^a & C_{24}^a & C_{25}^a & C_{26}^a \\ C_{13}^a & C_{23}^a & C_{11}^b & C_{12}^b & C_{13}^b & C_{33}^a \\ C_{14}^a & C_{24}^a & C_{12}^b & C_{22}^b & C_{23}^b & C_{34}^a \\ C_{15}^a & C_{25}^a & C_{13}^b & C_{23}^b & C_{33}^b & C_{35}^a \\ C_{16}^a & C_{26}^a & C_{33}^a & C_{34}^a & C_{35}^a & C_{36}^a \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{11} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{22} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{33} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{23} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{13} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{17}$$

where

$$C_{ij}^b = \alpha_{ij}/L \quad C_{ij}^a = \sum_{k=1}^N \varphi_k \left\{ C_{\chi}^{(k)} + \left\{ \begin{matrix} C_{j3}^{(k)} \\ C_{j4}^{(k)} \\ C_{j5}^{(k)} \end{matrix} \right\}^T \left\{ \begin{matrix} \bar{\omega}_{i1}^{(k)} \\ \bar{\omega}_{i2}^{(k)} \\ \bar{\omega}_{i3}^{(k)} \end{matrix} \right\} \right\} \quad (18)$$

for $i=1\sim 3$ and $j=1\sim 6$. The index $\chi=i$ except for $i=3$, $\chi=6$. The coefficients $\bar{\omega}_{ij}^{(k)}$ in Eqn (18) are

$$\bar{\omega}_{ij}^{(k)} = \beta_{jm}^{(k)} \bar{N}_{mi} + N_{ji}^{(k)} / Q_k \quad (19)$$

In above equations, the parameters are defined as

$$L = \det \begin{pmatrix} \bar{M}_{11} + R_N & \bar{M}_{12} & \bar{M}_{13} \\ \bar{M}_{12} & \bar{M}_{22} + R_{T_2} & \bar{M}_{23} \\ \bar{M}_{13} & \bar{M}_{23} & \bar{M}_{33} + R_{T_1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$\bar{M}_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\varphi_k M_{ij}^{(k)}}{Q_k} \quad \bar{N}_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\varphi_k N_{ij}^{(k)}}{Q_k} \quad (21)$$

$$R_N = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} R_n^{(k)} \quad R_{T_1} = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} R_{t_1}^{(k)} \quad R_{T_2} = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} R_{t_2}^{(k)} \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{11} &= (\bar{M}_{22} + R_{T_2})(\bar{M}_{33} + R_{T_1}) - \bar{M}_{23}^2 & \alpha_{22} &= (\bar{M}_{11} + R_N)(\bar{M}_{33} + R_{T_1}) - \bar{M}_{13}^2 \\ \alpha_{33} &= (\bar{M}_{11} + R_N)(\bar{M}_{22} + R_{T_2}) - \bar{M}_{12}^2 & \alpha_{12} &= \bar{M}_{13}\bar{M}_{23} - \bar{M}_{12}(\bar{M}_{33} + R_{T_1}) \\ \alpha_{13} &= \bar{M}_{12}\bar{M}_{23} - \bar{M}_{13}(\bar{M}_{22} + R_{T_2}) & \alpha_{23} &= \bar{M}_{12}\bar{M}_{13} - \bar{M}_{23}(\bar{M}_{11} + R_N) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \beta_{11}^{(k)} & \beta_{12}^{(k)} & \beta_{13}^{(k)} \\ \beta_{21}^{(k)} & \beta_{22}^{(k)} & \beta_{23}^{(k)} \\ \beta_{31}^{(k)} & \beta_{32}^{(k)} & \beta_{33}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} = -\frac{1}{LQ_k} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{11} & \alpha_{12} & \alpha_{13} \\ \alpha_{12} & \alpha_{22} & \alpha_{23} \\ \alpha_{13} & \alpha_{23} & \alpha_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} M_{11}^{(k)} & M_{12}^{(k)} & M_{13}^{(k)} \\ M_{12}^{(k)} & M_{22}^{(k)} & M_{23}^{(k)} \\ M_{13}^{(k)} & M_{23}^{(k)} & M_{33}^{(k)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

COMPLIANCE MATRIX

The compliance matrix can be gradually evaluated by solving the first order coefficients of the displacement fields under specific homogeneous traction boundary conditions. Once these coefficients are solved, the global strains can be readily obtained from the global-local strain relationship, Eqn (2), together with the stress-strain relationship of the constituent layers, Eqn (4). Elements of the stiffness matrix can be evaluated by dividing induced global strains to the specific global stress. Neglecting the algebraic detail, the compliance matrix is of the form

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\epsilon}_{11} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{22} \\ \bar{\epsilon}_{33} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{23} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{13} \\ \bar{\gamma}_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11}^a & S_{12}^a & \bar{\xi}_{11} & \bar{\xi}_{21} & \bar{\xi}_{31} & S_{13}^a \\ S_{12}^a & S_{22}^a & \bar{\xi}_{12} & \bar{\xi}_{22} & \bar{\xi}_{32} & S_{23}^a \\ \bar{\xi}_{11} & \bar{\xi}_{12} & S_{11}^b + R_N & S_{12}^b & S_{13}^b & \bar{\xi}_{13} \\ \bar{\xi}_{21} & \bar{\xi}_{22} & S_{12}^b & S_{22}^b + R_{T_1} & S_{23}^b & \bar{\xi}_{23} \\ \bar{\xi}_{31} & \bar{\xi}_{32} & S_{13}^b & S_{23}^b & S_{33}^b + R_{T_1} & \bar{\xi}_{33} \\ S_{13}^a & S_{23}^a & \bar{\xi}_{13} & \bar{\xi}_{23} & \bar{\xi}_{33} & S_{33}^a \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_{11} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{22} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{33} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{23} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{13} \\ \bar{\sigma}_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

where

$$S_{ij}^a = f_{ij}/T \quad S_{ij}^b = \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_k (\xi_{jm}^{(k)} P_{mi} + M_{ij}^{(k)} / Q_k) \quad \bar{\xi}_{ij} = -\sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_k \xi_{ij}^{(k)} = -\frac{1}{T} f_{jm} P_{mi} \quad (26)$$

The parameters in above equations are

$$T = \det \begin{pmatrix} F_{11} & F_{12} & F_{13} \\ F_{12} & F_{22} & F_{23} \\ F_{13} & F_{23} & F_{33} \end{pmatrix} \quad F_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \Phi_k \left(C_{\omega\omega}^{(k)} + \frac{1}{Q_k} \begin{pmatrix} N_{1j}^{(k)} \\ N_{2j}^{(k)} \\ N_{3j}^{(k)} \end{pmatrix}^T \begin{pmatrix} C_{\chi 3}^{(k)} \\ C_{\chi 4}^{(k)} \\ C_{\chi 5}^{(k)} \end{pmatrix} \right) \quad (27)$$

$$f_{11} = F_{22}F_{33} - F_{23}^2 \quad f_{22} = F_{11}F_{33} - F_{13}^2 \quad f_{33} = F_{11}F_{22} - F_{12}^2 \quad (28)$$

$$f_{23} = F_{12}F_{13} - F_{23}F_{11} \quad f_{13} = F_{12}F_{23} - F_{13}F_{22} \quad f_{12} = F_{23}F_{13} - F_{12}F_{33}$$

$$\xi_{ij}^{(k)} = -\frac{1}{TQ_k} N_{im}^{(k)} f_{mj} \quad P_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\Phi_k}{Q_k} \left(\begin{pmatrix} C_{3\alpha}^{(k)} \\ C_{4\alpha}^{(k)} \\ C_{5\alpha}^{(k)} \end{pmatrix}^T \begin{pmatrix} M_{1j}^{(k)} \\ M_{2j}^{(k)} \\ M_{3j}^{(k)} \end{pmatrix} \right) \quad (29)$$

In Eqn (27) and (29), $i, j=1\sim 3$. The indices ω equal to j except for $j=3$, $\omega=6$. It is noted from Eqn (25) that only three elements in the global compliance matrix, \bar{S}_{33} , \bar{S}_{44} and \bar{S}_{55} , are influenced by the imperfect bonding conditions.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Since generally anisotropy of each layer is assumed, other kinds of elastic properties of layers are degradations from this model. The degraded three dimensional constitutive relationships for layered media composed of orthotropic, transversely isotropic and isotropic layers are found to be the same as those derived by Sun and Li [10], Salomon [11] and Lai and Wang [7] (the former two are perfectly bonded cases). Numerical examples are made on the apparent E_{33} and G_{13} of a $[\pm 30]$ Kevlar/epoxy angle-plyed laminate and a three-phase inclined layered rock subjected to traction boundary conditions. Tables 1 and 2 are respectively the elastic properties of Kevlar/epoxy and the constituent phases of the layered rock.

Table 1. Elastic properties of Kevlar/epoxy [12]

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	E_{33} (GPa)	ν_{23}	ν_{13}	ν_{12}	G_{23} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)
161.880	10.600	10.600	0.313	0.313	0.313	4.037	5.890	5.890

Table 2. Elastic properties of the constituent phases of the three-phase layered rock

Layer Type	E (MPa)	ν	Volume Ratio
I	3.000	0.100	20%
II	2.000	0.200	30%
III	1.000	0.300	50%

The coordinate definition of the inclination of the layered rock is shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show the relationship between apparent E_{33} and G_{13} and the bonding parameters R_N and

R_T , where $R_T = R_{T1} = R_{T2}$. It is clear that these two elastic moduli are strongly affected by the bonding parameters.

Figure 3. Coordinate definition of the layered rock

Figure 4. Apparent E_{33} (left) and G_{13} (right) of the Kevlar/epoxy laminate under imperfect bonding conditions

Figure 5. Apparent E_{33} (left) and G_{13} (right) of the three-phase inclined layered rock under imperfect bonding conditions

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the flexible interface model, this paper provides a general three dimensional constitutive relationship for imperfectly bonded periodic multilayered media composed of generally anisotropic layers with 21 independent elastic moduli. Three parameters, which form a damage vector at each interface, can be used to describe the interface bonding conditions. The tangential bonding parameters, $R_{T1}^{(k)}$ and $R_{T2}^{(k)}$, can be readily obtained from direct shear test

at the k -th interface. On the other hand, the normal bonding parameter, $R_n^{(k)}$, was assumed to be valid only under tensile state to avoid overlap. However, a non-zero $R_n^{(k)}$ under compression is possible if the interface is initially slightly detached.

Under specific homogeneous boundary conditions, the stress and strain distributions within each layer, not included in this paper, can also be obtained during derivation process. These distributions are important in the study of failure criteria of a layered medium.

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